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"Psychology over Technology"

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software use. But the attention has always been paid successively in pre-service and in-service teacher training to hardware and software use, then to pedagogy and lastly to human factors. Most times technological innovations are implemented by looking people's behaviour, beliefs and skills. Perhaps, this has been the reason enough why innovation has failed more times. It poses an enormous, possible unique challenge on teacher as it demands considerable change in way of teaching (Sheingold & Haldey, 1990; Fullan, 1991; Wild, 1993).

Whilst some teacher can cope adequately with large scale change, others are far more conservative in nature. In fact, with regard to the adoption of computers, it has been found that teachers as a professional group are highly conservative (Adkisson, 1985; Gilman, 1989; Gunter, 2001; Feldman, 2004; Bhatia, 2008). Many teachers enjoy stability, see innovation as a threat and shun problems as undesirable. Though it is a proven fact that every change is uncomfortable. 'Almost every important learning experience we have ever had has been stressful' (Black, 1987).

Zayapragassarazan and Ramganes (2008) reported about 'technophobia' prevailing among teachers, which means any negative psychological reaction to technology. The factors responsible for such fear of or revulsion to ICT are age, race, gender, early experience, social status and residence. The teachers who shun ICT are generally the teachers who don't understand it or they are not used to it. Usually technophobia inflicts the older generation who hasn't grown up with ICT computers, computer games, complicated acronyms, or even calculators. Another thing that they dislike is the fact that they are being taught by those younger than them.

Teachers do not yet exploit the creative potential of ICT and engage students more actively in the production of knowledge. Teachers' use of

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ICT for communication with and between students is still in its infancy. ICT is underexploited to create learning environments where students are more actively engaged in the creation of knowledge rather than just being passive consumers (Kessel, 2005; Ramboll management, 2005; Ramboll management, 2006).

'The anxieties of uncertainty and the joys of mastery are central to the subjective meaning of educational change' (Fullan, 1991). Eraut's (1988) study of the uptake of Information technology in schools found computer using teachers who exhibited typically positive attributes- teachers who possess confidence, seek out opportunities for change, enjoy risk taking and are willing to work with new methods of learning. Nowadays learning in schools has to be more attractive and interesting to be meaningful for learners. The teacher is not merely to teach but to inspire the learners to seek knowledge, arouse curiosity, sustain interest and increase the span of attention. He has to be friend; philosopher and guide and not merely dispenser of knowledge. The teacher education institutions, therefore, required to equip future teachers for this new role by training them in the usage of ICT.

Teacher Educators are required to help future teachers to develop confident, positive, proactive attitudes so that they may cope more effectively with the challenges of technological innovations in schools. If teachers are to use ICT successfully in schools, they need to know how to cope with policies, programs and constraints of the organization they are working in. It is rarely possible for a single teacher's desire to use ICT in his/ her teaching and not to be affected by wider policy, time table, curricular and resource issues within a school. As schools like individuals can be conservative places as it is reported that schools have changed very little in the last century. (Cuban, 1984; Kerr, 1989; David, 1991; Pappert, 1993).

The ICT has revolutionized the teaching learning process at all levels and in all fields, but teacher education has not seen the light of the day (Chauhan, 2008). Thus, the challenge remains is to use ICT for education and if this has to happen in education, the change has to begin from the teacher education system. Teacher educators will have to assume new responsibilities and come out of phobia of the machine that it is something which has to be touched by somebody else. The reality is that it is very user friendly. The teacher will now use much less expensive and much more powerful multimedia for enhancing learning by customizing it to suit the needs of individual learner (Maheswari, 2003). Jayanthi and Padamanaban (2008) stated that there is a need to engineer a paradigm

shift from "Computer Education" to "Computer for Education" preferably ICT for education. ICT skills should be incorporated through curriculum and both teacher educator and trainees need ICT skills and capabilities.

In our country, ICT has been largely used by the entertainment industry and for business and commerce and changes have taken place in our life style. But what is the effect of these changes on teacher education? Are we prepared for taking advantage of it? If not, then what do we have to do and how do we prepare ourselves for it?

Our educational institutions cannot ignore this ever increasing pace of technological progress and their role in building ICT empowered citizens. But only those teachers who have ICT competencies can handle this technological advancement. Thus it becomes necessary to create in the teachers an awareness of the possibilities of ICT which will lead to their willingness to learn it and resulting in the commitment and confidence to use it. Thus teacher education institutions have important role to turn out ICT competent teacher through in-service and pre-service courses. (Dikshit, 2006; Garg et. al., 2008).

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